

20

23

**ANNUAL
REPORT**

Let's make life better

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FEMaLe 2023

Highlights

January

30 of the 65 deliverables submitted

600 WCE2023 abstracts submitted

FEMaLe adviser promotion #5, Mureddu

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

February

FEMaLe partner promotion, IAAD

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

Psychological interventions improve quality of life

[Read study here](#)

First monthly FEMaLe/ Endometriosis.org Glossary Post

April

FEMaLe adviser promotion #6, Jansen

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

FEMaLe webinar with WEO (World Endometriosis Organisations)

[Link to the YouTube playlist with four webinar videos.](#)

The long video is the webinar in its entirety and three shorter ones are the same content, but structured.

The background for MY-ENDO in FEMaLe Project

[Read the press release](#)

May

- The FEMaLe project pre-congress at #WCE2023 has kicked off

- Best Oral Presentation from an Early Career Scientist (FEMaLer Anna Melgaard)

- Adrienn Salamon elected to World Endometriosis Society Board

Ladywalk

- The Danish Parliament Health Committee Expert hearing

[Link to the LinkedIn post by FEMaLer Dorte Rytter](#)
(click translate at the bottom of the post if needed)

June

FEMaLe article:

The lived experiences of endometriosis in adolescence

[Read the article here](#)

FEMaLe represented at NCGE-NCE2023

[Read our LinkedIn post](#)

#EURAM2023

FEMaLe Liv went to Dublin to present the paper 'How Agile Practices Change in a Large Research and Innovations Project'

Data access agreement btw. PrecisionLife and University of Oxford

[Read precisionlife's LinkedIn post](#)

July

FEMaLe adviser highlight #7, Weckesser

[Read the highlight on our LinkedIn](#)

August

..... "Many women get this disease"

An op-ed by major Danish news paper "Politiken"

[Read the Danish \(and paywall'ed\) article here](#)

FEMaLer Anna Melgaard sheds light on delays in endometriosis diagnosis

[Read our LinkedIn post here](#)

..... FEMaLer highlight, Dorte Rytter

[Read our highlight on LinkedIn here](#)

September

..... FEMaLe & Innovation News Network

[Link to feature in Innovation News Network](#)

FEMaLe partner promotion, Oxford

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

..... FEMaLe & Innovation News Network

[Link to feature in Innovation News Network](#)

World's largest endometriosis study needs your help!

[Link to Semmelweis University press release](#)

October

MVA's Women's Health Network – Endometriosis

[Link to our post on LinkedIn](#)

FEMaLe partner promotion, Aarhus University Hospital

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

Symptom tracking in endometriosis using digital technologies

[Link to article](#)

November

Impact of a co-created endometriosis social media health campaign

[Read the article here](#)

FEMaLe adviser promotion #8, Broch

[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

Why politicians should prioritise a National Actionplan for #endometriosis?

[Link to our LinkedIn post](#)

Catenion report on 'Financing Innovation in Women's Health'

[Read our post on LinkedIn](#)

The graphic should do the explaining #proud

FEMaLe adviser promotion #9, Bharati
[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

FEMaLe in the EU!
[Watch the presentation playlist on YouTube](#)

December

FEMaLers just hosted esteemed
endometriosis expert Grant Montgomery
[Read Faezeh Darki's LinkedIn post](#)

FEMaLe partner promotion,
Aarhus University
[Watch the interview on YouTube](#)

WORK PACKAGE ACHIEVEMENTS / SUMMARY

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WP1 IMPACT

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP1 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- We have participated in and presented FEMaLe's use of Half Double Methodology at the European Academy of Management (EURAM) Conference in June 2023.
- Moreover, we provided a Case Study on the FEMaLe project's learnings from using Half Double for the upcoming book 'Project Management in Practice: Case Studies'.
- Finally, we delivered two guest lectures (May 2023 and Dec 2023) on FEMaLe's experiences with implementing Half Double at the PhD course on 'Project Management: A Practitioner's Approach to the Managerial Process'.

WP2 CODE

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP2 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- The white paper on ethical health and care systems seeks to stimulate talk about ethics in healthcare systems in general, explain the existing solutions and describe the current challenges. We highlight FEMaLe's cases, including how project partners are handling the ethical issues. Finally, we provide clear recommendations for next steps.
- The white paper on gender-based and inclusive health and care systems aims to gain a deeper understanding of gender and inclusion from an international perspective and provide an overview of how these factors may influence women's health and illness, with a particular focus on endometriosis. Finally, we provide recommendations to guide future actions.
- The white paper on RRI-oriented and Open Science health and care systems aims to gain a deeper understanding of how to work with Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in a European project and provide an overview of how this impacts the project's results. Finally, we provide recommendations to guide future actions.

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WP3 PHENOTYPE

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP3 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- With the aim of identifying and reaching consensus on relevant symptoms related to endometriosis, a baseline questionnaire was developed based on inputs from endometriosis patients, medical doctors and researchers specialised in endometriosis; consensus was reached on six relevant symptoms. A manuscript covering the results from the Delphi study is currently under preparation.

Results from WP3 were presented at the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:

* One Step Closer to the True Prevalence Of Endometriosis:
Results Of A Delphi Study (Poster)

- The results from the Delphi study contributed to the development of a survey questionnaire, which was sent to a random sample of 63,000 Danish women in the spring 2023. These data are currently being linked to updated Danish registry data and will be used to describe the geographical distribution of endometriosis-like symptoms in Denmark as well as a phenotypic description of women with endometriosis.

More results from WP3 were presented at the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:

* Endometriosis: Consequences of Delayed Diagnosis (Oral)

For the oral presentation, Anna Melgaard won the prize for Best Oral Presentation from an Early Career Scientists.

- A scientific paper comparing health care use in the 10 years preceding the endometriosis diagnosis with that of women without diagnosis, has been published in Human Reproduction in August 2023.

<https://academic.oup.com/humrep/article/38/10/1910/7242571>

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WP4 OMICS

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP4 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- We will identify combinatorial risk scores (CRS), i.e., combinations of SNP genotypes that together exhibit a non-linear epistatic effect on phenotype. We count directly how many cases-control members have these combinatorial features and how strongly they are associated with their phenotype. This not only gives a more accurate score, but also a much more personalized one.
- A genome-wide association study meta-analysis, including 60,674 cases and 701,926 controls of European and East Asian descent, identified 42 genome-wide significant loci comprising 49 distinct association signals. We observed significant genetic correlations between endometriosis and 11 pain conditions, including migraine, back and multisite chronic pain (MCP), as well as inflammatory conditions, including asthma and osteoarthritis. Multitrait genetic analyses identified substantial sharing of variants associated with endometriosis and MCP/migraine.

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41588-023-01323-z>

- Results from WP4 were presented at the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:
 - * Genetic Subtypes in Endometriosis Identified from Combinatorial Analytics (Oral).
 - * The Genetic Basis of Endometriosis and Comorbidity with Other Pain and Inflammatory Conditions (Oral).
 - * Defining the Proteomic Profiles for Endometriosis Sub-types (Poster).

WP5 BIG DATA

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP5 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- A baseline questionnaire and a longitudinal questionnaire were developed and implemented as an additional module in the Lucy app. It collects self-reported data on symptoms of endometriosis, socio-demographics, mental and physical health, economic, nutrition, and other lifestyle factors.

Data are collected in the following countries: Hungary, Denmark, Sweden, Germany, Austria, Italy, Romania, and Poland. Participant recruitment began in December 2021 and is expected to continue until December 2024.

- Results from WP5 were presented during the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:
 - * The Use of the Lucy App in Patient Profiling for Early Diagnosis of Endometriosis (Oral)
 - * Hey Lucy! Your best friend on hard days! Period tracker/menstruation calendar mobile application for the early recognition of menstrual diseases (Poster)

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WP6 DIAGNOSIS

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP6 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- We have demonstrated that applying deep learning techniques in medical image analysis is possible even with very diverse data, such as lesion images from laparoscopic video. One of the main aspects is addressing the challenges of cross-border image sharing, especially considering stringent regulations like GDPR.

Results from WP6 were presented during the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:

* Applying Cross-Border Machine Learning Approach for GDPR-protected Medical Data (Poster)

- A significant accomplishment is the development of efficient strategies for data preparation and dataset splitting. We have effectively mitigated the issue of data leakage between training and testing phases, ensuring the robustness of our models while preserving stratification - classes balance between train, test and validation sets.
- The successful integration of the algorithm into the Augmented Reality (AR) software marks a significant milestone for FEMaLe and for SurgAR company. Our algorithm, previously verified for its commendable frame rate of 40 frames per second during inference, has now been seamlessly incorporated into the AR software. This integration is the result of dedicated efforts by our skilled development team.

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WP7 VISUAL

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP7 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- Legal contracts with 5 health centers world-wide are made.
 - 247 confirmed (by experts) surgeries are collected.
 - 534 short video sequences are extracted.
 - 9,507 endometriosis lesions are totally annotated.
 - Annotated zones across 1,320 images with the team of expert and junior surgeons.
 - 60 person-hours of discussion to standardize the incision boundary guidelines and reach consensus.
 - Annotation pipeline is confirmed based on Delphi method.
 - Created a guidebook for data annotations with the effort of surgeons.
 - Deep neural network algorithm is designed, implemented and validated.
- Noorzadeh et al. Enhancing surgery in endometriosis laparoscopy: training neural networks to segment incision boundaries. *Art Int Surg* 2024;4:1-6. 10.20517/ais.2024.02.
 - The algorithm developed marks a substantial leap forward in the realm of surgical technology.

The algorithm will be integrated in the augmented reality (AR) software of SurgAR, a leading innovator in surgical technology.

Integration into SurgAR's AR platform signifies a transformative advancement in surgical practices, as it empowers surgeons with the ability to identify machine-generated suggestions for incisions in real-time.

This application holds immense promise for enhancing surgical precision and decision-making by providing surgeons with immediate, data-driven insights during procedures.

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WP8 DIGITAL

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP8 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- To maximise the impact of the MY-ENDO program, we conducted a qualitative feasibility study.
- A scientific article on the feasibility of the MY-ENDO program has been submitted for publication in an international scientific journal and is currently under review.
- A new GDPR-compliant research platform for the MY-ENDO program has been developed.
- The new research platform has been tested and evaluated by researchers and mindfulness experts and technical issues have been solved.
- The full MY-ENDO program has been pilot-tested on the new research platform, both the self-guided version and the therapist-guided version, by five patients with endometriosis.
- The content of the MY-ENDO program has been translated from Danish into English and Hungarian, and both translations have been linguistically validated.

- Results from WP8 were presented during the World Congress on Endometriosis in Edinburgh in May, 2023:

- * Developing a digital mindfulness- and acceptance-based intervention for endometriosis management (Oral).

- * The effects of a digital endometriosis self-management program – Protocol for a three-armed RCT (Poster)

- * Women with endometriosis experiences of receiving a digital mindfulness- and acceptance-based intervention for endometriosis management (Poster)

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WP9 BEACON

A selected few key FEMaLe outputs and highlights in WP9 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- FEMaLe LinkedIn account has gathered a community of 1,891 followers (333% increase).
- FEMaLe Twitter account has gathered a community of 1,497 followers (45% increase)
- FEMaLe Instagram account has gathered a community of 736 followers (120% increase)
- FEMaLe YouTube account has gathered a community of 26 subscribers (50% increase)
- FEMaLe Website has been continuously updated with latest news about activities and achievements.

WP10 GOVERNANCE

- We have utilized the Half Double Methodology – a state-of-the-art hybrid project management framework – to reduce time to impact, keep the project in motion and promote the leadership of people (FEMaLers). Leadership has been embracing uncertainty and being capable of handling unexpected changes by uniting all the different points of view and created a shared commitment to the common vision. We have set up Correlate FEMaLe as our dedicated knowledge management platform to support communication and collaboration, which can integrate seamlessly with other FEMaLe tools to optimize the flow of knowledge.

A selected few key FEMaLe project outputs and highlights in WP10 from July 2022 to December 2023:

- We have refined the FEMaLe Correlate platform as our dedicated Knowledge Management platform to support communication and collaboration in WP10, integrating seamlessly other tools to optimize the flow of knowledge. As an example, we embedded our Miro board into the Correlate platform and used all the Miro functionalities, while maintaining all sharing permissions and accesses.
- We have initiated research on archiving, which will influence how the FEMaLe Correlate platform will handle this process, supporting the realisation of FEMaLe's Digital Legacy.

FEMaLe SoMe metrics

Performance on Social Media

2023 in numbers

401 POSTS
430.304 REACHED
1.073 AVG. REACH / POST

LINKEDIN

1.944 FOLLOWERS
122 POSTS
259.145 VIEWS
2.124 AVG. VIEWS / POST

TWITTER

1.503 FOLLOWERS
135 POSTS
134.535 IMPRESSIONS
997 AVG. IMPRESSIONS / POST

INSTAGRAM

747 FOLLOWERS
144 POSTS
36.624 EXPOSURES
254 AVG. EXPOSURES / POST

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR 2023!

If you haven't done so already, please follow FEMaLe on social media and interact with us and the united endometriosis community!

click the icons to start to engage already today!

